

Leakage and infiltration detection techniques

Deliverable 2.4

Leakage and infiltration detection techniques

Deliverable 2.4

Summary

This report describes the work performed within Bodø Living Lab regarding Task 2.2 “Water-smart solutions for Bodø”. More specifically, subtask 2.2.1 involves monitoring and communication technologies, algorithms and approaches for leakage and infiltration/inflow quantification, detection and localization. It introduces the state-of-the-art for smart water meters, leakage quantification, detection and localization in water distribution networks and infiltration and inflow quantification and detection in sewer networks and how it was applied and extended during this project. The application of self-powered smart water meters allows for the acquisition, storage and communication of flow, pressure, temperature data with high temporal resolution of up to 1 minute. In conjunction with the existing district meters of the municipality, this data was the basis for both the application of existing methods for leakage quantification and the development of new data-driven algorithms for leak detection. To test those approaches an artificial leak scenario was designed and carried out in the field, providing openly available test data. For infiltration and inflow estimation, several methods were explored and evaluated for applicability resulting in the application of a method based on a sewer flow measurement campaign. Furthermore, a proof of concept for the possibility of modelling the interdependency between leakage out of the water distribution system and infiltration into the sewer was developed. Two dashboards are described, one providing homeowners with a detailed view of the consumption in the household, while the second is designed for application by the municipality.

Deliverable number	Work package
--------------------	--------------

D2.4	WP2
------	-----

Lead beneficiary	Milestone author(s)
------------------	---------------------

NORD	Ole-Marius Johansen, Vemund Kristiansen
------	---

Quality assurance

Maria do Céu Almeida (LNEC)

Contributors

Christian Petersen (TECHNI), Rachele Collette (Bodø Kommune), Bardia Roghani, Prasanna Mohan Doss, Franz Tscheikner-Gratl (NTNU) Panagiotis Kossieris, Archontia Lykou (ICCS), Camillo Bosco, Elhadi Abdalla (SINTEF)

Planned delivery date	Actual delivery date
-----------------------	----------------------

31/05/2024	07/07/2024
------------	-------------------

Dissemination level

- PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other program participants
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium.
Please specify: _____
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Table of contents

List of Figures	5
List of Tables	6
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	7
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Leakage	12
1.2 Infiltration and Inflow	13
2 Smart water meters at the households	15
2.1 State-of-the-art and beyond	15
2.2 Technology Description for Bodø	17
2.3 Experiences from the operational phase	19
2.3.1 Results	19
2.3.2 Challenges	20
2.3.3 Key findings	21
3 Data collection, storage, and distribution	22
3.1 State-of-the-art and beyond	22
3.2 Technology description for Bodø.....	22
3.3 Experiences from the operational phase	24
3.3.1 Results	24
3.3.2 Challenges	24
3.3.3 Key findings	24
4 Leakage detection methods and algorithms.....	26
4.1 State-of-the-art and beyond	26
4.2 Technology description for Bodø.....	29
4.3 Experiences from the operational phase	32
4.3.1 Results	34
4.3.2 Challenges	36
4.3.3 Key findings	36
5 Infiltration and Inflow	39
5.1 State-of-the-art and beyond	39
5.2 Technology Description for Bodø	43
5.3 Experiences from the operational phase	45
5.3.1 Results	46
5.3.2 Challenges	46
5.3.3 Key findings	47

6	Incorporation in project dashboards	48
6.1	Nessie platform	48
6.2	Environment Dashboard.....	50
7	Achieved Impacts	52
8	Conclusion.....	54
	References	54

List of figures

Figure 1: Involved technologies and tools in Task 2.2.1 and their interconnections..... 11

Figure 2: Estimated I/I volume in Norwegian wastewater treatment plants in 2022 (adapted from Jørgensen and May Rostad, 2022) 14

Figure 3: Energy usage calculation and battery lifetime as a function of the number of transmissions. 16

Figure 4: Cross section of the water meter. 18

Figure 5: Overview of Smart water meter installation, update, and uninstalls (blue means installed and functional, red installed and non-functional, yellow functioning but with incorrect data and X inspections carried out). 21

Figure 6: Simplified version of data collection and distribution system. 23

Figure 7: Methods for detecting leaks in Water Distribution Networks. 26

Figure 8: Front end of the SINTEF application to visualize the water balance components. 29

Figure 9: Three variants of the Encoder-Decoder Model used for Leak detection: (a) simple Autoencoder, (b) LSTM-AE and (c) Variational Autoencoder..... 31

Figure 10: Exemplary leak event showing the true leak (red line) and detected events (black lines) for sensors at different locations in a real-world network using reconstructions from the AE Model..... 32

Figure 11: The schematic of an isolated zone where leak experiments were conducted. Leaks are simulated at seven locations marked L1-L7 in blue. 33

Figure 12: Flow measurements obtained during leak experiments. Red dashed lines denote simulated leak events. 35

Figure 13: SWM pressure measurements obtained during leak experiments. 35

Figure 14: Signal reconstructions from the AE model on SWM pressures for leak detection with red lines indicating the artificial leaks. 37

Figure 15: SWM flow measurements obtained during leak experiments. The orange ellipse in SWM 14 indicates a possible in-house plumbing fault. 38

Figure 16: Methods for quantifying and localizing I/I (Ohlin Saletti, 2021). 39

Figure 17: The approach for interconnected I/I modelling by Jaurena Beltrami (2023). . 42

Figure 18: Installation of flowmeters inside the upstream and downstream manholes of the studied area. 43

Figure 19: The schematic of the study area and the locations of the flow meters. 44

Figure 20: Monthly precipitation data during the study period in Bodø, Norway. 45

Figure 21: The average flow values into/out of the study area during wet and dry weather conditions throughout the study period. 46

Figure 22: Nessie’s default dashboard. 49

Figure 23: Environment dashboard screenshot..... 50

List of tables

Table 1: SWM Resolution and logging and sending frequency. 17

Table 2: Summary of exploratory studies on leakage detection. 27

Table 3: Maximum leak flow rates, total volume, and leak duration of simulated leaks in the real network. 33

Table 4: Summary of exploratory studies on detection and quantification of I/I in sewer networks. 40

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AE	Autoencoder
API	Application Programming Interface
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
COVID	Coronavirus Disease
DMA	District Metered Area
DTS	Distributed Temperature Sensing
DWF	Dry Weather Flow
EC	European Commission
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographical Information System
IoT	Internet of Things
IR	Infrared
IWA	International Water Association
I/I	Infiltration/Inflow
LL	Living Lab
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LSTM	Long-Short-Term Memory
LSTM-AE	Long-Short-Term Memory Autoencoder
M	Month
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MNF	Minimum Night Flow
MSE	Minimum Squared Error
MVC	Model View Controller

NB-IoT	Narrowband IoT
NOK	Norwegian Currency
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SWM	Smart Water Meter
SWMM	Stormwater Management Model
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
WDN	Water Distribution Network
WDS	Water Distribution System
WNTR	Water Network Tool for Resilience
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The B-WaterSmart project focuses on critical aspects of water management in Bodø, a Norwegian town located above the Arctic Circle. This focus is on leakage in water distribution networks and the infiltration and inflow in sewers. The reduction of both is a high priority for all Norwegian municipalities and a goal worldwide. To support these efforts a variety of tasks were carried out in LL Bodø within the work package 2 of B-WaterSmart.

One part was the further development, testing and demonstration of self-powered household water meters. The developed water meter, differentiating it from all existing ones, uses a combination of a turbine/generator in combination with a bypassing valve for excess flow to generate the energy for the water meter from the flow of water. This allows for the collection and transmission of data with an increased temporal resolution of 1 min without external power source. Such data can be used to describe customer behaviour and water usage in detail and defining use cases as well as having an additional feature to detect leakages in the house plumbing system by observing the pressure behaviour. 28 of these meters were installed in households in a pilot area in Bodø measuring flow, pressure and temperature over a period of 9-12 months. These measurements together with the existing SCADA data of Bodø Kommune were used for method selection and testing.

Several methodologies (existing and newly developed) for leakage quantification, detection and localization in water distribution networks were tested for applicability. They ranged from water balance-based quantification, data-driven leak detection algorithms and model-based or hybrid leak localization. For LL Bodø an existing water-balance approach on a district metered area level was implemented and a novel leak detection algorithm based on three different machine-learning algorithms was applied. It was evaluated using an artificial leakage field experiment, where leaks were simulated by opening hydrants over a period of two days. The resulting dataset is openly available.

A second part consisted in applying the same procedure of testing and selecting for quantification and detection of infiltration and inflow in sewers. To enable this a 16-month flow measurement campaign at the in- and outlet in a sewer of the pilot area was conducted. After testing several novel approaches, the selected method best suited for LL Bodø's current needs was a flow-based method using the minimum night flow. The simplicity of the method allowed to build competence in using the measurement equipment and the data while providing insight in the functioning of the system. Furthermore, a modelling framework was developed to connect the leakage from the water distribution network with the infiltration and inflow into the sewer. This framework was tested on a realistic case study providing a proof of concept in areas where the water supply system and sewer system are using shared trenches.

Another important part was the data collection, transmission, and visualization of the data, newly collected and already available. This was done in collaboration with work package 3 and resulted in the development of two different dashboards for different user needs. One dashboard is designed for households to ensure water safety in homes and to raise homeowner's water consumption awareness, whereas the other dashboard has been developed for waterworks

operators which connects existing meters in the supply network to detect abnormal events swiftly. Combining data from smart water meters, municipal water meters, sewer flow meters, and demography, provides a detailed overview of the municipality's water use and facilitates better decision-making in infrastructure projects, supporting efficient resource allocation, infrastructure planning, and maintenance scheduling. These improvements lead to cost savings and enhanced service delivery.

Overall, these advancements contribute to sustainable water management practices, improve service delivery, ensure the long-term resilience of water and wastewater infrastructure and cost saving from early damage prevention, benefiting both communities and the environment.

1 Introduction

To meet the current legal requirements for both water and sewage infrastructure in Norway by 2040, it is estimated that investments of NOK 332 billion (approx. EUR 28.4 billion) are required (Norsk Vann Rapport 259, 2021). However, this investment forecast does not include potential new requirements. For example, the upcoming introduction of the new EU Wastewater Directive (UWWTD) is expected to lead to stricter requirements for wastewater treatment. While the exact details of these requirements are still being developed, Norway needs to anticipate and prepare for potential changes. In this sense, significant investments and strategic planning will be necessary to meet the challenges associated with ageing infrastructure and constantly changing regulations, both nationally and in the wider European context.

As part of task 2.2 “Water-smart solutions for Bodø”, more specifically subtask 2.2.1, [B-WaterSmart Living Lab Bodø](#) has been launched as a pilot study to improve the detection, quantification, and visualization of leaks in municipal water distribution systems as well as the infiltration/inflow (I/I) in sewer systems. In a selected area, smart water meters have been installed to measure the demand in water supply and flow meters were installed in the sewer system to allow for I/I quantification. Combined with existing available data from the municipality, this data was analysed using advanced algorithms (e.g., data analysis, machine learning), looking for anomalies in the data (e.g., pressure, flow) itself and compared to forecast system behaviour, and then visualized on two dashboards to provide insights into water usage patterns, potential leaks, and other anomalies. As tools and technologies are heavily interconnected, this report will traverse the boundaries between WP2 and WP3 by describing all the involved parts seen in Figure 1. The indicated tools (#29 and 30) and technologies (#14 and 15) started at a TRL5 and reached TRL7 at the end of the project, except for the algorithms (not patented but an open access solution) due to the limited extent and length of records, resulting in TRL 6.

Figure 1: Involved technologies and tools in Task 2.2.1 and their interconnections.

This provides the structure of the report. First, the smart water meters (in section 2) and the data distribution and storage (section 3) are described, then the various detection, quantification and localization algorithms for leakage (section 4) and I/I (section 5) are described, and finally the implementation into the dashboards (section 6). Subsequently, the achieved impacts are named (section 7). The focus on water distribution leakage and I/I into sewers is in line with the Norwegian Water Association sustainability goals that envision an overall reduction of the national water loss average to 20% by 2030 (Norsk Vann Rapport 239, 2018) and an overall reduction of I/I to sewer systems of 30% by the year 2030 (Norsk Vann Rapport 255, 2020). Leakage and I/I are also technical indicators that contribute to the assessment of water-smartness, which was developed in the B-WaterSmart project through Deliverable 6.3 (Silva et al., 2023), in direct form for transport efficiency in % for both water supply and sewers and indirectly into costs, environmental risks, and water availability (Shavi et al., 2021; Ugarelli et al., 2021).

1.1 Leakage

Water losses can be defined, e.g. by Lambert (2002), as the difference between system input volume and authorized consumption and consist of apparent losses and real losses. While apparent losses are caused by unauthorized consumption and all types of metering inaccuracies, real losses are described as the annual volumes lost through all types of leaks, bursts, and overflows on mains, service reservoirs, and service connections, up to the point of customer metering. These real losses are often referred to as leakage. There are several types of assessment methods developed for leakage assessment, which can be divided into top-down and bottom-up approaches (Puust et al., 2010). Top-down approaches focus on estimating the leakage in a system by examining the various components in the overall water balance (Farley, 2001), with a focus on the water consumption for different purposes. Meanwhile, the bottom-up leakage assessment uses 24-hour zone measurement and Minimum Night Flow (MNF) analysis, often as an extension of the top-down approach (Mutikanga et al., 2013).

In Norway, a slightly modified version of the International Water Association (IWA) standardized water balance method is applied, as is stipulated in Norsk Vann Rapport 239 (2018). This method can be applied on a system as well as a district metered area (DMA) level. Statistics Norway (<https://www.ssb.no/>) gives insight into the leakage rates with 30% nationwide and 21.5% in Bodø. The nationwide leakage is based on yearly manual reports from all municipalities, which are instructed to report in the percentage based on total delivered water and estimated consumption. Since only 38,7 % of homes in Norway have water meters installed, a common way of billing consumption for residents using the size of the house/apartment as a proxy. Consumption is then estimated by using an average person equivalent per m² and multiply it with a justifiable consumption per inhabitant. Together with the low number of water meters installed, this results in considerable uncertainty in the calculation by underestimating or overestimating the average consumption per inhabitant, which potentially makes the overall leakage percentage estimations unreliable.

Therefore, the approach in this deliverable (in section 4) is twofold: (1) introducing novel energy autarkic water meters at a household level and testing them over an extended period of time, and (2) applying suitable methods for leakage quantification, and developing new ones for detection and localization based on the available data.

1.2 Infiltration and Inflow

I/I (Weiß et al., 2002), also known as extraneous water or parasitic flows (Van Assel et al., 2023), is an extensive problem causing costs to society in various ways with costs mainly due to wastewater treatment plant investments and basement flooding events (Ohlin Saletti et al., 2023). It can be defined as undesired water entering the sewer system. Infiltration is water other than sanitary wastewater that enters a sewer system from the ground through defective pipes, pipe joints, connections, or manholes. Infiltration does not include inflow, which is water other than sanitary wastewater that enters a sewer system from sources such as roof leaders, cellar/foundation drains, yard drains, area drains, drains from springs and swampy areas, manhole covers, cross connections between storm sewers and sanitary sewers, and catch basins. Inflow does not include infiltration.

Unwanted infiltration into the wastewater system can lead to the reduction of the capacity of the wastewater system and even capacity exceedance in extreme cases (Beheshti and Sægrov, 2018). Inflow and infiltration cause environmental and economic impacts (Sola et al., 2020). The increased cost is related to sewer pump maintenance and operation, treatment plant and pipe capacity, and compensation for flooded basements due to capacity issues. The environmental impacts are related to poor treatment due to irregular loading in volume and quality and overflow of untreated water to receiving water bodies due to exceeding capacity (De Bénédittis and Bertrand-Krajewski, 2005).

In Norway, it is estimated that the percentage of I/I at wastewater treatment plants is as high as 66%, based on dilution calculations using total phosphorus as an indicator (Jenssen Sola et al., 2018). The methods applied to estimate I/I volume also include a water balance-based method (Norsk Vann Rapport 255, 2020). This is estimated by comparing the collected volume of water in the system with the expected volume of dry weather flow. It uses measured amounts of water led to a given measuring point to calculate the quantity of I/I-water. To use this method, one must make assumptions of the total number of persons and industry connected to the pipes upstream the measuring point and on the water consumption per person and day. Furthermore, 50% of leakages from drinking water end up as I/I water in Norway (Norsk Vann Rapport 255, 2020), because drinking water pipes and wastewater pipes are prevalently situated in the same trench (Sola et al., 2019), with water pipe trenches sharing 60% of their trench volume with sewers (Daulat et al., 2024).

Figure 2 shows the variability in I/I volume between municipalities of varying sizes.

Figure 2: Estimated I/I volume in Norwegian wastewater treatment plants in 2022 (adapted from Jørgensen and Rostad, 2022)

Consequently, the approach in this deliverable (in section 5) is twofold: (1) apply and develop suitable methods for I/I quantification and detection based on the available data, and (2) showcase the possibility of including the interconnected between water supply leakage and I/I.

2 Smart water meters at the households

Urban water systems in a digital age promise substantial advantages for service users, providers, as well as for society (Moy de Vitry et al., 2019). To fulfil this promise monitoring of the systems is a necessity. The most widely accepted smart water architecture is characterized by five layers: the physical layer, sensing and control layer, collection and communication layer, data management and display layer, and data fusion and analysis layer. (Li et al., 2020). Physical assets, such as pipes, valves, and pumps are elements that produce the required data and information, which would be collected, transferred, processed, and made available by internet-related hardware, software, and services. They also provide the structural foundation for the placement and installation of cyber instruments like smart meters. In return, those cyber instruments can inform the operation and maintenance of physical components by analysing the newly produced data and forecasting the system performance and condition. These meters are the focus of our research in LL Bodø. They can be used for the gathering of data on varying temporal and spatial scales. This data can then be used for water end uses characterization and user modelling, which could lead to personalized water demand strategies (Cominola et al., 2015). Whilst offering greater flexibility, higher sampling frequencies both in data collection and transmission present new and complex challenges for the water sector, in particular, data management, interpretation, and analysis requirements. The issue of data privacy is also of mounting contention and one that will demand the attention of utilities and regulators (Boyle et al., 2013).

2.1 State-of-the-art and beyond

In the current market, water meters based on ultrasonic flow measurements and impeller-based measurements are the most common. State-of-the-art SWMs are well represented by the water meter [AXIOMA QALCOSONIC W1](#), commonly used in Norway (e.g., in Asker near Oslo). It has an Internal battery – type 1x LS1425 3,6V Li.SOCL2 SAFT 18057C044 (1200mA), with an indicated lifetime of 13 years. The important limitation is the number of data transmissions per 24 hours while there is still energy left for the intended operational life of the meter, typically 15 years. The meter calculates its projected lifetime when requested, based on the selected data transmission frequency. The water meter has a representative performance concerning the upper limit of data it is possible to receive from these meters.

In an energy balance calculation forecasting 16 years (see Figure 3) between the energy needed for measurement and transmission and the energy inherent in the battery, we can see that the battery would deplete after seven to eight years and typically 13,000 transmissions. Based on these 13,000 transmissions, data could be transmitted only five times per 24 hours and contain the aggregated consumption at the transmission point. With AXIOMA W1, as an example of the typical state-of-the-art water meter in the market, it is evident from the energy balance calculation and logging of actual energy consumption, that no battery-based water meter can provide frequent, on a minute or even hour level, data over a longer period using a NB-IoT network.

Figure 3: Energy usage calculation and battery lifetime as a function of the number of transmissions.

The newly developed smart water meters improved in B-WaterSmart have some essential capabilities that are beyond the current state of the art in terms of transmission frequency while performing on par with the water meters in the market regarding measurement accuracy. The developed meters log, store, and send a larger amount of data. Data measured and transmitted with a high temporal frequency, in Bodø every 60 seconds, provides water consumption data to the end user with reduced delay. This would not be possible if the meter would be relying on an on-board battery alone (compare with the energy usage calculation in Figure 3). The developed water meters use a combination of a shut valve and a pressure transducer with a resolution of 0.1 bar on the house side of the valve to detect leakages in the piping system of the house. This integrated leak detection is only possible with this novel meter combining the controllable valve and pressure sensor with sufficient energy from its on-board turbine. The leakage detection is done by closing the integrated valve of the meter and performing a pressure logging based on the pressure sensor in the meter. The pressure sensor indicates a potential leak in the building based on a measured pressure drop.

The temperature sensors of the device measuring the air temperature of the air surrounding the device can give indications of a higher probability of condensation challenges. The temperature data can also be used to inform the house owner of potential challenges with frozen pipes. The SWMs differ from other water meters in the market with their ability for two-way communication. The communication from the server to the meter allows for several new features of the water meter. Adjustments of sending and logging frequency from the server side allow for the adaptation of selected meters for model calibration logging with high resolution over selected periods. The SWMs have a shutoff valve, and for security reasons, the communication implemented is secured with a certificate-based X.509 encryption. The encryption ensures the security of the data and in these meters, allowing two-way communication.

2.2 Technology description for Bodø

Before the project, the first demonstrator of the meter had been developed and the first test conducted. This first version had the radio modem as a stand-alone unit and was powered by power from the mains. A complete integration of a different modem and a new main board has been developed all with ultra-low energy consumption. Turbine energy harvesting optimized for low-pressure drop has been solved. As part of the project, a fundamental development and integration of sub-systems has been executed forming a platform for a meter with an increased performance versus all other meters in the market. In the current implementation of the technology platform in the smart water meters installed in Bodø, the following measurements are implemented for data transmission every 60 seconds: water pressure, water flow, water temperature, and ambient temperature.

In connection with the analytics of the device, additional information concerning the charge state of the onboard battery is logged and transmitted. This information has been important concerning the main question of energy status for the water meter over time. The question is a sustainable balance point between energy generated from the water flow and the energy consumption of the meter.

The following capability is at hand on the main board and as part of the technology platform, but not fully implemented due to several factors, primarily end-user privacy and a decision not to implement a server-side application for the shut-off valve. The following capability is at hand on the main board for future functionality.

- Humidity sensor, as an onboard sensor for internal water ingress in the meter electronics
- Microphone for acoustic leak detection, as the electronics hardware foundation for future leak detection algorithms. The system would be able to use the microphone for detection inside and outside the house transmitting the acoustic signals, which can be interpreted by algorithms.
- Shut off valve control, for the control of the “Water-Stop” ball valve included in the meter.

In the current version (see Table 1 for more information), the data is locally stored in the memory of the device and sent to the server at set intervals and in some instances, these are triggered by events. An example of an event is a reduction of data transmission frequency to once an hour when no additional water flow has been detected for the last 24 hours.

Table 1: SWM Resolution and logging and sending frequency.

Parameter	Frequency	Resolution
Water Volume	Consumption in the last 60s, in L	8 ml per step
Pressure	Every 60s	0,1 bar
Temperature	1/h	0,1 degree
Battery	1/h	0,01 Volt

The unique, for a water meter, high sampling and transmission frequency of 60 s allows for a multitude of improvements in the use of the measured data. It provides insight in the fluctuations of the flows and pressure, which allows to detect anomalies faster that would be smoothed out when the data is collected and transmitted only hourly or daily. It also allows for more detailed water usage characterization. The frequent data transmission allows for a new user experience with a higher degree of instantaneity. The rationale for the instantaneity, is the improved insight from a delay under 60 s and the motivation for change in water consumption behaviour driven by this. Regular water meters in the market do not send data frequently enough to generate a strong engagement from the end user. As exemplified a typical water meter would not be able to submit data more than a few times per 24 hours.

The accuracy class of the developed water meter is set to Class 2 according to OIML R 49-1 (2013) allowing $\pm 2\%$ for the upper and $\pm 5\%$ for the lower flow rates. A typical impeller from a meter in the market is used and the values in loop testing and calibration indicate a meter within this accuracy class. For the industrialised version of the product, the accuracy will be reconfirmed in a third-party flow loop.

The developed water meter (see Figure 4), differentiating it from all existing water meters, uses a combination of a turbine/generator in combination with a bypassing valve for excess flow to generate the energy for the water meter from the flow of water. The main challenge is the optimal harvesting of energy from low flow rates without introducing a large pressure drop at higher flow rates. The generated energy is regulated and fed to the on-board battery via a battery management circuit. In addition to the energy side, the water meter has an extremely energy-efficient main board for logging processing and storage of data. On the main board, the communication modem is implemented concerning energy efficiency.

Figure 4: Cross section of the water meter.

The water meter uses a measurement turbine from an analogue meter with an addition of a magnet being read by a hall sensor on the main board. The shut-off valve and valve control actuator are off the shelf components.

The concept and schematics for the electronics with ultra-low energy consumption were developed following the development of a model for energy balance. The goal is ultra-low energy consumption, especially in a state of sleep. Based on the energy balance modelling it was decided to improve the turbine efficiency and include an axial flow check valve for the higher flow rates. To extract the most energy possible, the turbine would need to be optimised for low flow rates and by-passing implemented for higher flow rates.

Thorough attention was given to both the main board and modem card, encompassing detailed design work and software development. Simultaneously, meticulous scrutiny was applied to the mechanical components, leveraging advanced flow simulations to refine the turbine housing and optimize fluid dynamics. During the development phase of the project, several adaptations have been made. The main board design and the processor capacity were selected for the collection and processing of acoustic data. In the version of the water meter built for field testing, these features were not implemented due to concerns regarding homeowners' privacy. The design and production phase of the SWMs during the COVID pandemic, was extremely challenging, primarily due to limited access to components. The electronic design had to be adapted and redeveloped according to the availability of components in the market.

2.3 Experiences from the operational phase

The field testing of the smart meters was conducted to verify a multitude of questions from the design phase of the water meter. The most important one is connected to the energy balance of the water meter in different real-world water consumption scenarios. In addition to testing the energy balance the connection from the modem in the water meter to the network was tested under various circumstances and water consumption habits. The robustness of the electronics in potentially high condensation environments was also a concern in the development phase.

2.3.1 Results

The energy balance of the SWMs indicates that a sustainable balance has been achieved. This means that an inflow and outflow from the battery is guaranteed in a manner that projects a "infinite" life from an energy point of view at 60 seconds data transmission. The energy level of most meters remained at a high level. The water meters did connect to the network for a majority of the meters. A group of meters lost their connection at a high charge state, but at this point, the underlying reason has not been identified. Condensation has been observed on the outside of several water meters, but internally in the housing, no water or onsets of corrosion has been found. Apart from one water meter with a drifting pressure sensor, the pressure data has been consistently reported from all the meters. All the meters have provided water and ambient temperature data consistently.

2.3.2 Challenges

The delivery and installation of the SWM have been delayed due to several reasons throughout the project.

Pandemic component parts and redesign delay: The challenge was managing the development, building, and testing of the product in a situation with reduced and severely delayed availability of modem and main processors for the products. The costly and calendar time-consuming solution was to change the design of the electronics according to the availability of components. The main components, modems, and processors were sourced in two different versions to ensure that they would accommodate the needs of the project. Re-calibration of the energy balance models was also necessary following the design changes. This significantly delayed the installations of the SWMs as well as decreased the quantity of SWMs available. Also, water quality sensors originally planned as part of the meter could not be incorporated. This was partly substituted by increasing the temporal granularity of the dataset, providing an open-source data set not yet available.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) delay: The GDPR documentation needed before any smart water meters could be installed proved to be more complex than foreseen. This documentation included data processor agreements, risk analysis matrices and homeowner contracts. This complexity stemmed from the transferring of data between various data processors (research groups and technology developers in the project), which is not commonly encountered outside of research purposes. The documentation took a total of 4 months (January 2023-May 2023) from start to finish and required a high level of legal and technical expertise from all parties involved.

Security certificate delay: From June 2023 - August 2023 there was a loss of connection with the five smart water meters installed as well as rendering all SWMs needing updating. Investigation revealed that this issue was caused by a Microsoft update, which rendered a certificate out of date. Techni addressed the issue by updating all the SWMs' certificates by August 2023.

Volunteer participation challenges in installing SWMs in private residences: Finding enough willing participants proved more difficult than anticipated. This was due to the pilot area being in a densely compacted area where split housing units sharing one water meter was extremely common. In this case, all homeowners would have to consent to installation. In hindsight, the type of residences within the pilot area should have been highly prioritized to minimize the time spent contacting several homeowners.

Loss of sensors and troubleshooting: 13 of the 28 SWMs installed have stopped transmitting data between October 2023 and April 2024. Two site visits were conducted one on February 29th, 2024, and the other on April 23rd, 2024. On-site inspections did not identify the underlying reason for power loss or loss of connection. An overview of the installations, updates and inspections can be seen in Figure 5. Blue means installed and functional. Red indicates “installed but non-functional.” The X denotes inspections. WM3.1 and WM3.2 are two different SWMs switched out at the same address whereas WM5.1 and WM5.2 are the same SWM but reside at different residences. WM14, the yellow row, continued to send data but the pressure and flow readings were incorrect.

	2023								2024					
	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June
WM1			X											
WM2				X										
WM3.1									X					
WM3.2														
WM4				X										
WM5.1			X											
WM5.2												X		
WM6														
WM7														
WM8														
WM9														
WM10														
WM11														
WM12										X				
WM13												X		
WM14										X		X		
WM15														
WM16														
WM17														
WM18														
WM19														
WM20														
WM21														
WM22												X		
WM23												X		
WM24										X				
WM25														
WM26														
WM27														
WM28										X		X		

Figure 5: Overview of Smart water meter installation, update, and uninstalls (blue means “installed and functional”, red “installed and non-functional”, yellow “functioning but with incorrect data” and X “inspections carried out”).

Noise complaints: Several homeowners have reported that the noise generated by the smart water meter turbines can be quite disruptive. In one instance, we removed a smart water meter installed on the neighbouring wall of a sleeping quarter due to excessive noise. Additionally, the municipality took action to address noise concerns for another resident by installing a barrier around the SWM to minimize its sound output.

2.3.3 Key findings

The field tests confirm the energy balancing simulation executed in development as we observe that a sustainable energy balance has been found in most of the water meters, meaning the generated energy balances the consumption of energy at the given logging resolution and sending frequency. The sending frequency was set to once every 60 seconds, and this proved not to be overambitious. A few of the meters lost their connection at a high charge state and displayed a low charge state when visited during inspection. At the time of writing, it is not conclusive how this has occurred, but the current hypothesis is that repeated connection attempts drained the battery.

An additional key finding from the field test is an observation of a turbine sound during water flow. The sound is conducted by the piping of the house. In the next revision of the water meter, an improvement of the turbine concerning sound will be needed.

3 Data collection, storage, and distribution

The data sources involved in the project include the SCADA system of the municipality's water supply network, IoT flow sensors in the wastewater system, and Smart Water Meters in residential households. These data sources have distinct characteristics and provide the basis for analytic tasks and research projects. By storing the data in a centralized location, the analytic tasks, and the distribution of the necessary data to the interested parties were made much easier (see also Santos Clotas et al., 2023).

3.1 State-of-the-art and beyond

SCADA systems are commonly used to monitor and control water distribution systems. They provide access to real-time monitoring and control for the personnel working directly with the water distribution system. As those systems are considered critical infrastructure, access to SCADA systems is restricted, even though the data produced can be of interest for parties outside the operations department. SCADA system specifications, functionality, features, and setup vary based on the vendor.

To make data from SCADA systems readily available without putting the system at unnecessary risk, sending it to a database outside of the restricted system is one solution. This database can also receive data from other (open or municipal) sources like smart water meters, IoT sensors, weather data, etc. By using APIs for accessing this database, users of the data can receive access to the data they need while preventing access to data they don't need. With this approach, many users with various needs can be served, while keeping the data secure.

Having access to well-documented validated data with a known uncertainty from the SCADA systems, smart water meters, and IoT sensors from a common database, allows studies to be conducted with near real-time data, as well as historical data from the duration of the project. IoT sensors monitor sewer flow (see chapter 5.2), smart water meters monitor the potable water usage of homeowners, data from water distribution network (via SCADA), and data from public weather services is made available via APIs. By collecting detailed data over time, reports and benchmarking can be done forming a basis when planning projects or strategic plans involving water and wastewater infrastructure.

3.2 Technology description for Bodø

Data is gathered from various sources, each with distinct characteristics, some send a continuous stream of data while others send a batch of data samples at certain time intervals. Sensors utilize different transmission methods like LoRaWAN and Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) to transmit data to the central system. In Bodø, NB-IoT from a telecommunications operator is utilized for the project. Furthermore, a LoRaWAN network is established to explore an alternative communication approach. It is essential to evaluate network coverage for both methods, with experience indicating that partnering with a commercial telecommunications operator is the most straightforward choice in terms of coverage and data security. Insufficient radio coverage may result in increased power consumption and reduced battery life. In Norway, LoRaWAN

operates in an unlicensed frequency band, potentially facing competition from other activities that could disrupt reliable communication.

To render the data usable for end-users, raw data is converted into a [FIWARE](#)-compatible format before storage in the database. The architecture, as depicted in Figure 6, is designed to minimize steps in the incoming data stream, simplifying troubleshooting and cost reduction. The system operates on the Microsoft Azure cloud platform, chosen due to prior familiarity and the data centre containing the database's location in Norway.

Figure 6: Simplified version of data collection and distribution system.

Since sensor characteristics of the SCADA system had huge variations (varying from 100s of data points per day to 10.000s of data points per day), it was decided to batch the raw data into averages of 10 minutes, 60 minutes, and 24 hours, as well as storing the raw data for the sensors. This data is then transformed into a FIWARE-compatible format before being stored in the database. To create data on a zone level (district-metered area), periodic tasks are run to calculate consumption in a zone, by fetching the relevant sensor averages from the database and performing calculations based on whether the sensor is measuring water into or out of a zone. The result from these calculations is then stored in the database. By performing these

calculations periodically, any requests for data on a zone basis, need only the results from the calculations, instead of fetching 100s or 10,000s of data points on a sensor level, and then making the calculations, for every request concerning zone data. The data is made accessible from various APIs that cover the use cases by dashboards and researchers in B-WaterSmart LL Bodø's SWM case study.

3.3 Experiences from the operational phase

When using data from SCADA systems, sensors as well as SWMs, having reliable connections proved to be difficult to always achieve 100% of the time. Sensors failing, sensors losing connection or construction work within a DMA are some examples that will affect the calculations. A strategy for managing such scenarios might be necessary if the data generated is going to be used for purposes demanding highly accurate data.

3.3.1 Results

Data from the municipal water meter SCADA system, IoT sensors, and smart water meters (SWMs) is stored and distributed reliably while keeping costs low. The data is available in various resolutions, enabling the fulfilment of requirements for hourly data as well as broader analyses over months and years.

3.3.2 Challenges

Since the number of sensors involved has huge variations in characteristics, it was sometimes complex to troubleshoot why some data was missing. Given that missing data often did not produce any error messages or had any pattern, a step-by-step approach was often necessary to find which step failed in the data processing stream. Also, some of the initial solutions selected for data processing were practically free to use while the amount of data being processed was relatively small. As more and more data were being processed, pricing increased to the point that changes had to be made to make the solution economically feasible, while still reliably performing the necessary tasks. The new solution was less than 1/10 of the original cost but did require some work to become as reliable as the original solution.

3.3.3 Key findings

Cloud Platform Selection: Utilizing [Microsoft Azure](#) as the cloud platform for hosting the database proved to be a strategic choice, offering rapid deployment, high availability, and comprehensive documentation.

Efficient Data Handling: The cloud platform's tools enabled efficient handling and analysis of large volumes of incoming data, facilitating real-time transformations and preliminary analysis before storage.

Reliable Data Distribution: Data sourced from diverse sources, including municipal water meter SCADA systems, IoT sensors, and Smart Water Meters (SWMs), was reliably stored and distributed, ensuring accessibility at various resolutions to meet different analytical needs.

Challenges in Data Management: Dealing with the variability in sensor characteristics presented challenges, particularly in diagnosing instances of missing data. A methodical troubleshooting approach was required to identify breakdowns in the data processing pipeline.

Economic Optimization: Initial cost-effective data processing solutions became economically unfeasible as data volumes increased. Adjustments were made to optimise costs while maintaining reliability, significantly reducing expenditure without compromising performance.

Refinement for Reliability: While achieving cost savings, efforts were directed towards refining the revised solution to ensure it matched the reliability of the original setup, highlighting the importance of balancing cost-effectiveness with system robustness.

4 Leakage detection methods and algorithms

We introduced leakage detection algorithms suitable for the Bodø case study, that were tested with the measured data from the SWMs, but also with existing data from the existing municipal water meter SCADA system, representative real-world data from comparable case studies, model-derived data from the Bodø hydraulic model and artificial benchmark data from literature (in this order of preference), to compensate for the delays of measured data from the SWMs (as described in the challenges in section 2.3.2). These leakage detection algorithms add an application potential and showcase the value of the SWMs data in a water distribution system contributing to the improved system performance at a household level.

4.1 State-of-the-art and beyond

There exists a wide variety of leak detection methods in the literature, and it is difficult to have a comprehensive understanding without broadly classifying them based on their working principles. One of the earliest studies by Wang et al. (2001) classified leak detection into four broad categories (see Figure 7) – (1) Offline methods, based on direct inspections and observations, (2) online methods referring to monitoring of large diameter pipes using moving pistons, (3) acoustic methods based on acoustic signal analysis and (4) hydraulic methods based on mass and energy conservation laws.

Figure 7: Methods for detecting leaks in Water Distribution Networks.

Out of these four families of methods, techniques within 1 and 2 are time-consuming and manual-intensive processes that are useful for pinpointing the exact location of leaks. They encompass a wide variety of hardware methods (Kammoun et al., 2022) ranging from gas tracers (Azwar and Nurhajati, 2017), endoscopy (Liu and Kleiner, 2013), ground penetrating radar (De

Coster et al., 2019), thermographic cameras (Bach and Kodikara, 2017) to fibre-optical sensing (Jacobsz and Jahnke, 2020). Acoustic methods (Hunaidi et al., 2000) rely on robust sound signal strength against background noise during data sampling and analysis. They are useful for detecting leak zones as well as pinpointing leak locations. However, the placement of acoustic sensors poses challenges during installations and analysis due to background noise.

The fourth category of leak detection, namely hydraulic methods has been widely used in the past decade. These methods can further be classified into two categories: steady-state methods and transient methods. The transient methods involve time and frequency domain analysis of available measurements for detecting leaks (Colombo et al., 2009). This class of techniques are, however, complex to scale for larger networks. On the other hand, the steady-state methods use mass and energy conservation laws as founding principles and the hydraulic equations are solved for a finite time. Any mismatch between the model predictions and available measurements is then used for determining the presence and approximate location of leaks. Recently, there have been numerous studies that explicitly use measurements for making inferences about network behaviour using machine learning approaches. These methods are classified as data-driven methods and have gained significant interest among researchers and practitioners in the water industry. A detailed description of those approaches can be found in Hu et al. (2021).

Based on the availability of data at LL Bodø different ways forward were investigated in various scales ranging from water balance models on a DMA scale to data-driven leak detection to model-based leak localization. Also, the project required an understanding of the current nature of Norwegian WDNs in general and direct efforts towards developing methods for Bodø LL, while data for Bodø itself was available relatively late. This resulted in several research methodologies being tested on a variety of representative datasets. The tested approaches and the used datasets with links to the full text of the works can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of exploratory studies on leakage detection.

Title	Short Description	Input → Output	Dataset
<p><u>Water loss management and data quality assessment in medium-sized water distribution systems in Norway</u> (Vimme, 2021)</p>	<p>Analysis of DMA level leakages and uncertainty analysis using the water balance method and minimum night flow analysis, based on Norsk Vann Rapport 239(2018)</p>	<p>Flow measurements → Water balance (on municipality and DMA level), DMA priority rankings for leak reduction measures</p>	<p>Real-world data from a Norwegian WDN</p>

Title	Short Description	Input → Output	Dataset
<u>Assessment of pressure-pipe life expectancy and pressure-leakage relationships in the water distribution system in Bergen, Norway</u> (Alaya, 2022)	Analysis of leakage levels using pressure-burst relationship models	Flow and pressure measurements → Reduction in leakage levels and pipe life expectancy	Real-world data from a Norwegian WDN
<u>Detection of leakages in a water distribution network using an autoencoder</u> (Totland, 2022)	Detection of abrupt bursts with a simple data-driven method (autoencoder with 13 different architectures) and threshold functions	Flow and pressure measurements → Detection of pipe bursts	Artificial case study L-Town (Vrachimis et al., 2022)
<u>Leak localization using a dual model approach</u> (Nordahl, 2022)	Estimate leak locations using a pressure-leak duality modelling approach based on the approach of Steffelbauer et al. (2022)	Flow and pressure measurements and hydraulic model → leak location	Real-world data from a European WDN (Steffelbauer, 2018)

The outcome of these explorative studies was the definition of the methods applicable for LL Bodø. It was decided that a water balance approach would be applied to conform with Norwegian guidelines (Norsk Vann Rapport 239, 2018), although expecting a similar level of uncertainty as observed in the data of a comparable case study due the low number of water meters at the consumers (Vimme, 2021). As they were clustered in one area, the approach would look at a DMA level to display the differences. Furthermore, the dual model approach (Nordahl, 2022) and the data-driven leak detection method (Totland, 2022) both showed promising results. However, there is limited research on the usage of granular flow and pressure measurement data for improving leak detection performance. Also, a benchmarking approach by Habenicht (2023) and other studies on similar systems (Tornyeviadzi and Seidu, 2023) showed more promise in the data-driven approaches. This, together with the uncalibrated hydraulic model of Bodø and the expectation of data from the SCADA system and the SWMs, led to the evaluation of data-driven models for leak detection encompassing real-time measurements from smart water meters and existing sensors in WDNs.

4.2 Technology description for Bodø

For the water balance model, SINTEF built an application based on the API of the Environmental Dashboard (tool #30) to enable the estimations of water losses and associated indicators, by considering the different components of the water balance based on a standard and well-established methodology (Lambert and Hirner, 2000; Lambert, 2002). The user can calculate periodic water balances with inputs entered manually or automatically. The automatic water balance estimations allow for the continuous monitoring of real and apparent losses, as well as revenue or non-revenue water, pointing out if and how a burst or increase of background leakage occurs over time. For illustration purposes, an image with an example of a water balance displayed in the front end of the developed application is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Front end of the SINTEF application to visualize the water balance components.

The user can select a customized time window for the calculation of the water balance and associated indicators. In the back end of the application, it is possible to connect real-time data coming from the different meters, including the smart water meters. The increased number of water meters implies that the water balance acquires greater accuracy for a given period, thanks to the automatic association of metered consumptions.

The inputs for the calculation of a water balance can be overwritten by the user, displaying in real time the results provided with the given variations. This opens possibilities to look at different scenarios and how results are affected by different inputs, with trustworthy measurements being the first option but being able to compare these with the current state of the art in Norway based on surrogates. The application also allows the user to save multiple water balances related to different periods to allow the comparison of the water balance components over time. In addition to the activities connected with the water balance, the modelling of Bodø's district equipped with Techni smart meters has been conducted. The outcomes of the water balance are reflected in the water distribution network model to improve the overall model calibration and related possibilities to identify leaks along the network.

The proposed data-driven leakage detection algorithms were based on deep learning techniques, as they are comprehensive for modelling complex patterns from SWMs. The main advantage of deep learning-based leak detection is that it can provide useful information, especially when the availability of a calibrated hydraulic model is not guaranteed, e.g., because of missing demand data. This scenario is extremely common among water industries since the need for iterative calibration procedures is complex and time-consuming. Hence, the researchers resorted to the data-driven models for leak detection using encoder-decoder models. However, the following assumptions must be (implicitly) met for implementation: (i) a sufficient number of sensors is available in the network, (ii) measurements are available for nominal system states that represent no-leak scenarios over a sufficient period of time, and (iii) data quality for the measurements is high enough to allow for training and application of the algorithms, or at least for adequate data pre-processing.

To evaluate the applicability of deep-learning models, three classes of encoder-decoder models were developed – (i) Simple autoencoder (AE), (ii) Long Short-Term Memory Autoencoder (LSTM-AE) and Variational Autoencoder (VAE). These models take pressure measurements as inputs and reconstruct those signals as outputs. If there exists one or more leaks in the network, the reconstructions from these models vary significantly representing the onset of leaks.

Autoencoders (Baldi, 2012) are a special type of deep neural networks that reconstruct an original input signal $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ as $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ while minimising the error function $\mathcal{L}(x, \hat{x})$. For continuous time signals, the error function could be Minimum Squared Error (MSE) or Mean Absolute Error (MAE) depending on the scale and distribution of the input signal. Autoencoders are analogous to Principal Component Analysis in non-linear space. It consists of two sections in its architecture – an encoder and a decoder. Encoder transforms $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ to a lower dimensional space $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ ($m < n$) while preserving the non-linearities and maximum variance. The decoder again transforms z to original dimension as $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. The reconstruction error will be high if there is a significant change in its distribution and thus can be attributed as the onset of a leak event.

One of the main limitations of autoencoders is that the autocorrelations of input signals are not well captured. To overcome this limitation, *Long-Short Term Memory* (LSTM) models (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997) are stacked in an encoding-decoding fashion to learn the autocorrelations and to predict longer sequence into the future (Srivastava et al., 2016). Hence *Long-Short Term Memory Autoencoders* (LSTM-AE) models can predict leaks ahead of time, provided the magnitude of leaks is higher than the noise distributions of input signals. The third deep neural model we consider for leak detection is *Variational Autoencoders* (VAE). Unlike AEs, VAEs are probabilistic and generative models that learn from sampling the latent space constrained with a Gaussian as a prior distribution (Kingma and Welling, 2022). Since the latent variable z is sampled from the conditional prior, VAE can be used to generate new signals with similar trends and better predictions for leak events while accounting for input noise.

To determine the onset of a leak, a sliding window technique is used to track the statistical discrepancy between two sub-sequences of the error time series (Truong et al., 2020). The three models are implemented using standard Python packages for data processing and Pytorch (Paszke et al., 2019) for neural network implementation. The schematic of these deep-learning models is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Three variants of the Encoder-Decoder Model used for Leak detection: (a) simple Autoencoder, (b) LSTM-AE and (c) Variational Autoencoder.

The development process started by testing on an artificial benchmark network whose operating scenarios closely resemble a typical real-world WDN (Vrachimis et al., 2022). The results of this testing can be found in Mohan Doss et al. (2023, 2022). The comparisons showed that the algorithms performed on par with other data-driven methods (Daniel et al., 2022; Tornyeviadzi and Seidu, 2023) with lower false positive rates.

The advantages of an artificial case study lie in the availability of data in sufficient quality and quantity to train and test those algorithms. This is not inherently true for real-world case studies, and the impact of varying data was a concern during development. The evaluation of models and their successful implementation is entirely dependent on the availability of good-quality data. Due to the challenges in SWM installation (see section 2.3.2) not enough data was available at the end of the algorithm development phase for validation, resulting in a significant delay in analysis. As an interim solution, a few adaptations have been for validation purposes. The models were also evaluated for a Norwegian WDN using only available measurements to evaluate their applicability to real-world systems. As the dataset also contained noise and missing values, data imputation and filtering were carried out using linear interpolations followed by the Savitzky-

Golay filtering (Schafer, 2011) process. The main finding was these models were quite accurate in determining leaks with large flow rates ($>5\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$), but their accuracy is greatly impacted by the quality of available data and the placement of sensors. An exemplary leak event in the real-world network and detected fault using the Autoencoder model is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Exemplary leak event showing the true leak (red line) and detected events (black lines) for sensors at different locations in a real-world network using reconstructions from the AE Model.

4.3 Experiences from the operational phase

For the operational phase specific to the case study area, a dedicated zone within the Bodø WDN was isolated for the leak detection study. In this zone, 17 smart water meters were installed and monitored for a few weeks for their reliability and data quality. Out of this, one location had 3 SWMs installed in the same location inside the multi-storied building (SWM 10). This specific zone was also isolated such that there exists no redundant inflow or multiple outflows from this zone. This zone's total flow into and out was measured using dedicated flow-measuring devices at higher resolutions. Based on the validation mentioned in section 2.2) the testing in LL Bodø was planned. As the time horizon grew shorter an artificial leak series was designed to allow for the application of the algorithms. The schematic of this isolated zone is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The schematic of an isolated zone where leak experiments were conducted. Leaks are simulated at seven locations marked L1-L7 in blue.

Following these preliminary checks, NTNU and Bodø Municipality worked together to conduct leak tests in September 2023. The experiments were conducted at various times during the daytime and midnight to take typical consumer behaviour into account. During experiments and data collection, Techni and Nordkontakt collaborated to ensure data transmission and storage for further analysis. The details of leak experiments are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Maximum leak flow rates, total volume, and leak duration of simulated leaks in the real network.

Leak location	Maximum Flow rate (m ³ /h)	Leak time (min)	Total volume (m ³)
L1	28.80	13.00	6.30
	7.20	15.00	1.99
	1.08	32.00	0.65

Leak location	Maximum Flow rate (m ³ /h)	Leak time (min)	Total volume (m ³)
L2	28.80	13.00	7.00
	3.20	18.00	1.03
	0.78	30.00	0.44
L3	29.20	11.00	5.76
	3.02	14.00	0.99
	0.75	30.00	0.42
L4	28.80	10.00	4.95
	3.00	15.00	0.87
	0.70	30.00	0.36
L5	28.90	10.00	6.46
	3.00	15.00	0.87
	0.72	30.00	0.43
L6	27.40	9.00	3.90
	3.10	15.00	0.97
	0.70	30.00	0.49
L7	29.50	11.00	7.04
	3.00	15.00	0.86
	0.71	30.00	0.45

4.3.1 Results

The leaks were simulated by opening fire hydrants at several locations within the isolated zone and the amount of leak was measured using an ad hoc measuring device close to the leak point. This measurement rendered it important to simulate different leak levels. Three distinct leak flow rates were achieved between (0.7 – 29 m³/h) at each of the leak simulation points. The obtained flow measurements from the inflow sensor are shown in Figure 12 and pressure measurements from SWM locations are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Flow measurements obtained during leak experiments. Red dashed lines denote simulated leak events.

SWM instantaneous pressures between 24-Sep-2023 to 26-Sep-2023

Figure 13: SWM pressure measurements obtained during leak experiments.

4.3.2 Challenges

The installation and data collection from the Techni SWMs posed a significant challenge for evaluating the leak detection methods. Apart from SWM data, the possibility of simulating multiple leaks was not feasible due to operational and practical constraints. Inflow and outflow measurements obtained from the Bodø Municipality also had multiple repeated samples as with some measurements from Techni SWM. To tackle this, data preprocessing was done carefully to discard spurious samples and remove duplicates. Out of 17 SWMs that were installed inside the dedicated isolated zone, two SWMs (SWM 1 and SWM 5) had significant missing data and therefore cannot be used for analysis.

4.3.3 Key findings

The obtained pressure and flow data from SWM did not show any correlations concerning leak events. This was also evaluated using analysis of signal reconstructions from the AE models, as shown in Figure 14. The red dashed lines show the timestamps at which leaks were simulated. The reconstruction errors did not necessarily correspond to the leak events except for SWM 14 for the first few leak events on 25th September 2023.

Figure 14: Signal reconstructions from the AE model on SWM pressures for leak detection with red lines indicating the artificial leaks.

The inflow measurements, however, obtained from Bodø Municipality’s DMA system reflected simulated leak events as visualized in Figure 12. Further, despite no significant changes in pressure measurements from SWMs, the flow measurement from SWM 14 showed a possible

inhouse plumbing fault and significant variations during simulated leaks as shown in Figure 15. This indicates that in-house leaks could be detected with the availability of SWMs as long as the uncertainty matches the sampling frequency, but in the current setup not for the distribution system. As most detection techniques require a continuous stream of high-resolution measurements and these requirements are not fully satisfied by most of the domestic smart meters, because of both the scarce resolution of the water meters and the limited autonomy of the battery-powered electronics (Pietrosanto et al., 2021), the SWM developed (see section 2) can provide such a dataset.

Figure 15: SWM flow measurements obtained during leak experiments. The orange ellipse in SWM 14 indicates a possible in-house plumbing fault.

In addition, with the availability of granular data from SWMs and flow measurements from Bodø Municipality, it is also possible to do micro-calibration of WDNs. This will lead to multiple applications in terms of model calibration, predicting consumption behaviour, hybrid modelling strategies for leak detection etc. The data set from the experimental setup is currently anonymized and will be made available to the research community and other interested parties at the end of the project (e.g., on <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) to stimulate further research as currently, no such dataset is openly available.

5 Infiltration and Inflow

We introduce I/I algorithms and technologies suitable for the Bodø case study. The initial idea was to use the widely distributed measurements at the WDN in combination with the newly installed household meters as indicators for I/I as well. The finally available dataset proves not to be sufficient in temporal and spatial scale to develop such an approach for LL Bodø. However, a proof of concept using a realistic case on the combined evaluation of water distribution leakage and sewer I/I is shown.

5.1 State-of-the-art and beyond

Numerous techniques have been proposed to tackle the issue of excess water resulting from I/I in sewage networks (Hey et al., 2016). Different methods for detecting, localising, and quantifying I/I can be categorised into quantitative methods for assessing the magnitude, volume, and discharge of I/I, and qualitative methods for detecting the location of I/I sources (Beheshti et al., 2015). Based on the principles they apply they can be further distinguished into sub-groups, which is summarised in Figure 16.

Inspection-based	Temperature-based	Tracer-based	Flow-based	Model-based	Digital water
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical inspection • Closed circuit television 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributed temperature sensing • Infra-Red cameras 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pollutant time series • Stable isotope • Dye • Smoke testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dry weather flow • Moving minimum • Water balance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrological • Hydraulic • Data-driven 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online monitoring • Data processing • Visualization

Figure 16: Methods for quantifying and localizing I/I (adapted from Ohlin Saletti, 2021).

For decades, discharge measurements and their correlations with rainfall data have supported sewer managers in the investigation of infiltration and/or misconnections in separate sewers. For combined or domestic sewage, the statistical analysis of discharge data (reference flows or wastewater quality parameters, such as nutrients, and electrical conductivity) during dry weather days over a long-term time series is the widest applied method to quantify infiltration. Seasonal tendencies of the minimal flow rate (typically, in the middle of the night) deliver information on existing infiltration (De Bénédictis and Bertrand-Krajewski, 2005). In separate sewer systems, a positive correlation between discharges and rainfall data indicates misconnections towards the sewage.

On the other hand, closed-circuit television (CCTV), visual and smoke inspections provide better information regarding the locations of I/I entry into sewers. Also, tracer experiments are widely used either to quantify infiltration or pinpoint misconnections in separate sewer systems (Ellis and Butler, 2015). Visual inspection is limited by the fact that the inflows being detected are not always continuous, thus this inspection will only identify active inflows (e.g., during a rain event or when an illicit connection is in use).

Distributed temperature sensing (DTS) has the potential to both detect and locate I/I. Temperature changes are a strong indication of an incoming flow, which could be infiltration, licit or illicit connections. Thermography is mainly used for detecting infiltration or illicit connections. Fibre optics are deployed commercially at a relatively small scale offering distributed temperature sensing. DTS can detect inflows and illicit connections while using the difference in the thermal footprint of different water sources (Beheshti and Sægrov, 2018; Hoes et al., 2009). This method can measure for an extended period but is spatially limited by the length of the cable and by the high cost of its application. Mounting an infrared (IR) camera on a moving/flying platform (Lepot et al., 2017) could increase the inspectable length. Both solutions (DTS and internal use of an IR camera) deliver an accurate location of the inflow since the thermal effect of the lateral connection can be monitored immediately downstream and can be applied without service disruption. By comparison to the CCTV footage, the thermal fingerprint allows the type of connection to be identified (warm or cold) giving an additional key to pinpoint the source of infiltration.

Panasiuk et al. (2022) directly compared a range of techniques, concluding that the methods studied showed variable performance and that a combination of two or three methods would improve the efficiency of investigations. It should be noted that certain assumptions and restrictions apply to any technique used to address I/I in sewerage systems (Beheshti et al., 2015). Because of this, there isn't a single, widely applicable approach; instead, the best approach depends on the specific circumstances of each instance, including its constraints.

In the initial phase of the B-WaterSmart project, efforts were directed towards identifying the most suitable method for addressing the I/I challenges specific to the Bodø LL case study. This endeavour involved the formulation and carrying out of several exploratory research projects shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of exploratory studies on detection and quantification of I/I in sewer networks.

Title	Short description	Input → Output	Dataset
Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for Detection of Inflow and Infiltration Water in Sewer Systems (Søvik, 2021)	Using LSTM to predict Dry weather Flow (DWF)	Pumping station data (Outflow, sump level), precipitation, temperature, tide level → I/I volume	Bergen Municipality (Norway)
Flow Measurements Derived from Camera Footage Using an Open-Source Ecosystem (Meier et al., 2022)	Utilizing off-the-shelf cameras and convolutional neural networks to estimate the discharge in open sewer channels	Camera footage → Water Level and Surface Velocity	Lab setting

Title	Short description	Input → Output	Dataset
Using Optical Velocimetry to Detect Illicit Inflow to Sewers (Løfald, 2023)	Usage of camera footage to find wrong connections in a system	Video frames and rainfall data → velocity, illicit inflow	European case study
Quantifying Infiltration and Inflow in Data-Scarce Environments (Skagsoset, 2023)	Finding the correlation of flows with external data (e.g., precipitation) Calculation of expected flows in wastewater system using available pump station data	Pumping data (Flow, on-off), GIS Data → SWMM model, I/I volume	Horten Municipality (Norway)

These studies showed possibilities for the approach of LL Bodø. However, the machine learning approach (Søvik, 2021) in combination with the data scarcity on the sewer system flow data seemed unwise to follow. The two technological approaches (Løfald, 2023; Meier et al., 2022) were too far from proven and validated to be further tested. The approach of Skagsoset (2023) in combination with the statistical evaluation of discharge measurements (Karpf and Krebs, 2011) and their correlations with rainfall data, as proven and tested methods seemed the best way forward. As a result, this investigation aimed to track sewer flow over 13 months with high temporal resolution and use the data for I/I assessment in small, isolated service area, similar to the approach of Ye et al. (2023).

To combine those measurements with the SWMs and leak estimates, Jaurena Beltrami (2023) investigated [the interconnectivity of urban water system models](#) and the infiltration of leaked water from the water network into the sewer pipes through a combination of [EPANET](#) and [SWMM](#) based on studies done by Zhang et al. (2021). The conceptual model developed to identify and model the relations between the water distribution system and the sewer network is presented in Figure 17.

The demand required in the water distribution system is comprised mainly of users' demands and possible leaks occurring in the network. The water leaked will infiltrate into the ground nearby. Once infiltrated, it can become part of the groundwater or enter the sewer system through defects in the pipes. So, two links can be established between the water distribution network and the sewer system. The household demands are related to the sewer household discharges, and the leaks from the water distribution system can end up in the sewer system. When it comes to modelling, both the water and sewer networks can be well represented using EPANET, in this case using WNTR (Klise et al., 2018), and SWMM, in this case swmmR (Leutnant et al., 2019), respectively.

The demand's link was established by two possible methods including transferring the water supply demands directly to the sewer inflows (based on Lund et al. (2021)) and applying a transfer factor to represent losses that can occur from the moment the water is consumed until it is discharged (based on Zhang et al. (2021)). Additionally, a method to describe the non-rain derived infiltration into the sewer due to leakage from the water distribution network was suggested. The method was based on the model proposed by Karpf and Krebs (2011) for infiltration of groundwater into the sewer and modified based on engineering assumptions to adapt it for infiltration of water pipe leaks.

Figure 17: The approach for interconnected I/I modelling by Jaurena Beltrami (2023).

The results confirmed the feasibility of this approach and can be seen as a proof of concept in a Norwegian case study. The established links and models can simulate the system behaviour, however a higher amount of data for validation is necessary. Regarding the household modelling, it is recommended that further work focus on adding a time lag to the demands before discharging into the sewer system. Also, the modelling of leaks relies on assumptions that require additional validation to enhance their reliability. For further details, interested readers are encouraged to consult Jaurena Beltrami (2023). Due to the challenges in SWM installation the approach was not followed through and validated in LL Bodø, though.

5.2 Technology description for Bodø

The investigation was based on the recorded data from part of the Bodø sewer system in Norway. With the help of technicians from Bodø municipality, the flowmeters (two [NivuFlow Mobile 750](#) devices) were installed separately in the upstream and downstream manholes of the examined region (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Installation of flowmeters inside the upstream and downstream manholes of the studied area.

Figure 19 shows the study's area's schematic (anonymized for data security), which includes the flow meters' placements (In- and Outflow). All the pipes, with a total length of 642 m, in the research area are composed of plastic, primarily PVC. Diameters range from DN100 (132m), 160 (168m), and 200 (307m) to DN225 (35m). The flow was expected to consist of purely wastewater as it is part of a completely separated system. The main branch of the system has 5 incoming branches of which 3 were connected in manholes and 2 along the pipe.

Figure 19: The schematic of the study area and the locations of the flow meters.

Over the measurement period of 13 months the sensors were checked regularly for their functionality in-situ and in between the data was constantly observed on-line, as described by Bertrand-Krajewski et al. (2021), and when necessary, the sensors were maintained to sustain data quality (in our case plausibility, synchronicity, calibration, and maintenance). In the current study, two [NivuFlow Mobile 750](#) devices were utilized to measure the flow into and out of the study area. The flow velocity measurement method is based on the ultrasound reflection principle, and data transmission is automatic. Water level is estimated using pressure measurements from a bottom sensor and transit time with ultrasound from a sensor at the top of the pipe. The equipment was calibrated before installation at the site. The primary calibration was performed at the Hydraulic Laboratory of NTNU. It should be noted that for detecting outliers in this study, a Z-test was applied with a window containing 5 timesteps (2 timesteps before and 2 timesteps after the data under study). In the case of missing data, the average of the timesteps was used as a replacement. Like any measurement device, occasional missing values were encountered in the data. In such instances, the average of two consecutive time steps forward and two backwards was used as a substitute for the missing value. Additionally, periodic accumulation of debris in front of the sensors necessitated intervention by technicians to enter the manhole and clear it.

Regarding the precipitation, external data from the Bodø Skivika station SN82310 were downloaded from [Norsk KlimaServiceSenter](#). The precipitation data, available with a 1-minute temporal resolution, is measured, quality controlled and pre-processed by the station operators (NVE) and the performance and exposure category is defined as C2. Monthly precipitation data during the study period is illustrated in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Monthly precipitation data during the study period in Bodø, Norway.

The overall effluent flow can be separated into four distinct components (EPA, 1990):

1. Sanitary flow is correlated with residential water use, institutional flows, and wastewater from commercial and industrial operations.
2. Groundwater infiltration is the term used to describe the water in the soil that seeps into the network through the joints.
3. Direct rainfall, which comprises melting snow and rainwater that enters networks through manhole covers and faulty connections, among other factors.
4. Rain-induced infiltration water is the water that seeps into the network through soil penetration during rainstorms.

Dry weather flow is the wastewater flow rate that results only from sanitary flow and groundwater penetration (items 1 & 2). In other words, it exclusively refers to water that flows through pipes when there aren't any precipitation occurrences. Considering there is almost no consumption or sanitary flow between the hours of 0 and 6 am (particularly in small towns), the total flow that is observed during this period is equivalent to the infiltration of groundwater (during dry spells). Access to precipitation records, which are required to ascertain the beginning and ending periods of rainfall episodes, is essential to addressing items 3 and 4. Estimating direct precipitation and rain-induced infiltration requires this information. Since the minimal night flow (MNF) approach is widely employed and well-described in the literature in Scandinavia (e.g., Lundblad and Backö, 2012), it was chosen for this investigation as one of the most prevalent methods to estimate the amount of infiltration into the system. The fundamental concept of this approach is the continuous flow of (groundwater) infiltration. Here, we assume that, during a dry period, the least quantity of infiltration occurs between 3:00 and 5:00 in the morning (Pangle et al., 2022).

5.3 Experiences from the operational phase

This study is one of the few in Norway to continuously monitor sewer flow in a well-defined and limited area with a temporal resolution of 5 minutes for 16 months. Here, the main question is to

determine the proportion of flow in the studied area attributable to I/I during the study period, on average, and to identify its source. In this case, the focus was laid on well-tested and proven methodology and its impact and first-time application in a utility with similar challenges and possibilities as LL Bodø to allow a more effective use in practice of available knowledge/tools, as well as capacity building for the involved personnel.

5.3.1 Results

Figure 21 shows the analysis of the data that was recorded during the study period. The analysis of MNF values during dry weather flow circumstances reveals that the assessed system's groundwater penetration rate is around 0.7 litres per second. If we assume constant water consumption at night during the study period, comparing the MNF at the study area's entrance during the dry and wet seasons indicates an extra inflowed water of about 0.25 litres per second from the upper zone during the rainy season.

Figure 21: The average flow values into/out of the study area during wet and dry weather conditions throughout the study period. The shaded areas show the min and max values.

Examining flow estimates at the research region's entry and exit points during rainy seasons, however, reveals notable differences that point to a significant inflow into the study area. In particular, the maximum average flow rate at the point of exit is 3.3 times greater and the MNF value is almost 4.3 times higher during the rainy season than it is during the dry period.

5.3.2 Challenges

The challenges here were mainly part of the common procedure of setting up any measurement campaign, with the additional problems induced by the climate conditions (frozen shut manholes etc.). The first months were used to estimate a balance between the temporal resolution of

measurement and transmission with the energy consumption and the connected need for battery exchange and maintenance. Apart from that the challenge of external data availability and system knowledge occurred. While in the data an obvious correlation with rainfall events was visible the system data would have not supported this as being a fully separated system. Local knowledge of the system by the operators, which was not fully implemented in the system data, solved this, and led to the correct conclusion.

5.3.3 Key findings

Following discussions with the municipality of Bodø, it was discovered that a stormwater pipe branch was present, totalling more than 80 meters in length. It was found that these branches, which had diameters between 110 and 200 mm, were directly connected to the sewage system. The results of this study highlight the value of flow measurement investigations in detecting a variety of problems, including illicit rainwater connections and improperly connected stormwater pipes to the sewage network, even though in this case, the municipality was previously aware of these inappropriate connections. The method has proven robust and easily applicable for the utility.

6 Incorporation in project dashboards

Two separate dashboards have been developed to cover the different needs of homeowners and technical personnel. The Nessie platform (6.1) covers the homeowners, while the Environment dashboard (6.2) gives the technical personnel and the municipality's administration easy access to the current situation for the entire municipality's water supply. Here only a short description is given, more detailed information can be found in [Deliverable 3.4](#) (Santos Clotas et al., 2023).

6.1 Nessie platform

The Nessie platform is an information system, developed within ICCS/NTUA, able to acquire, process and store, and in general, to manage, high-resolution (up to secondly) data from IoT agents, such as sensors and smart meters, coupled with analytics (to translate the data into information) and visualisation capabilities to present the information to the end-users. In the framework of B-WaterSmart, the Nessie system (tool #29) was expanded to meet the requirements and needs of the Bodø case, focusing on the development of a digital platform that allows householders to monitor and manage the water consumption of their households. Building on experience from past projects, the Nessie system has been customised, evolved, and enhanced to support the fast, reliable, interoperable, and real-time retrieval of data, their processing and communication to third-party systems, as well as their presentation to the end-users via a new dashboard. In the context of B-WaterSmart, we go one step further and we are developing the new generation of Nessie, called “Nessie as a Service (NaaS)”, to allow the seamless integration of Nessie core system with external systems, developed by third-party entities, through a flexible state-of-art API. Apart from the functionalities that allow the different data sources and third-party models/algorithms to communicate with the core Nessie platform, NaaS allows the creation of entire environments managed by third-party partners. Additionally, a fully upgraded new user interface has been developed, comprising fully customisable dashboard features, easily adjusted by the householder (selection of the type of data to be presented, selection of the visual display, selection of advanced widgets etc). The new system has been implemented in the context of the FIWARE standard, establishing communication with the FIWARE Context Broker (i.e., Orion or Stelio) to consume data according to NGSI-V2 & NGSI-LD requests. The above new technology is implemented in the Bodø case to retrieve data from smart meters, and integrate Nessie with the new analytics/applications that are being developed i.e., the advanced analytic that breaks down (disaggregates) the total water consumptions, as measured by the smart water meters, into the various water-related uses (e.g., taps, washing machine, dishwasher, garden irrigation) and customise the dashboard to the peculiarities to Bodø's end-users (householders).

From the end-user's point of view, the Nessie system is a digital environment which enables homeowners to access data on water consumption, water quality temperature, pressure, etc. transmitted from the installed water smart meters in their households. The system can be accessed by using <https://bws.uwmh.eu/account/login/>. It requires login credentials that have been provided to the end-users.

In the context of B-WaterSmart and regarding homeowners' experience, a new user interface has been developed with various new features that allow them to create their custom dashboards by selecting different widgets for several purposes (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Nessie's default dashboard.

Data on the dashboards are real-time and graphs/values are automatically updated thanks to the FIWARE-enabled architecture and Nessie as a Service configuration and setup. The system is highly adjustable and configurable to align with homeowners' needs. While using the system, end-users may access the data and search for any specific period and time scale. For example, a homeowner may decide to access data for the last 30 days and explore the water consumption recorded every day, every minute, or every week.

For end-users' convenience, a default dashboard has been set up for them to be able to see from the homepage called "My Dashboards":

- The latest hourly measurements of water consumption and temperature.
- The water consumption and temperature at an hourly scale for the last 2 days.
- The average water consumption per day of the week based on all measurements recorded so far by the smart meters.

- The average water consumption per hour based on all measurements recorded so far by the smart meters.
- Water consumption recorded during daytime compared to nighttime.
- Water consumption recorded during weekdays compared to weekend days.

The above information can be changed according to end-users' needs and interests and they may change the information presented or re-arrange it as they wish through the available widgets.

Through Nessie's capabilities, the end-users can access different widgets and advanced analytics that can help them to increase awareness, check the water consumption per use and eventually lead them towards taking actions to reduce total consumption. They are also able to detect any potential leakages while seeing in real-time water consumption that is higher than usual.

6.2 Environment Dashboard

The environment dashboard (tool #30) is a web application that is based on the ASP.NET MVC framework. The framework provides dynamic web content, integration with databases/APIs and other features that are useful for creating and maintaining websites. ASP.NET Razor and JavaScript are the primary technologies used to make the dashboard interactive. Google Maps, Google Charts and Apache ECharts are used to display/visualize the data. With Google Maps, map layers are used to visualize water zones, with the option to change the colour of the zone based on data about that specific zone. A detailed view of the data is provided with interactive and non-interactive graphs by using the Google Charts library and Apache ECharts. The language of the website is English by default, but Norwegian language is also available if the browser language is set to Norwegian (Norsk Bokmål). An exemplary screenshot is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Environment dashboard screenshot.

It is designed to give an overview of the situation in the water distribution system. Zones are dynamically outlined on a map, while graphs display various data depending on selections and key information when clicking on zones in the map. Primarily designed to be useful to technical personnel or other interested parties wanting information regarding the status of the water distribution system.

In the backend, there are enormous amounts of data from the municipality's water meters in the supply network (see Figure 6). This meter data is structured so that you can select both a time slot, geographical area and, at the bottom, also the individual meter. In the project, we have also experimented with different methods for visualizing data. Bars, graphs, and donuts to explore what is experienced best. Demographic data has also been added so that one gets an impression of how consumption reflects the number of inhabitants. As of today, there is a weakness as water consumption for various industries has not been extracted. But there is room for that in the further development of the dashboard.

7 Achieved Impacts

The project's advancements in water meter technology, leakage detection, mapping and monitoring infiltration, and operational monitoring have significant impacts on the water smartness of LL Bodø and beyond:

Enhanced Smart Water Meter Technology: The developed water meters represent a step forward in efficiency and functionality. By enabling substantial data logging, leak detection, and two-way communication with the server, these meters provide accurate water usage information, potentially saving both water and money for homeowners, municipalities, and water operators. Additionally, the inclusion of temperature sensors can prevent costly damages from frozen pipes in older homes or cabins in cold climates. The meters' ability to generate their power and ensure secure communication enhances their reliability and security, which is crucial for maintaining a reliable water supply and protecting sensitive data.

Advancements in Leakage Detection Algorithms: By identifying leaks more accurately and quickly than the currently applied methods, these algorithms help conserve water resources, reduce water loss, and minimize infrastructure damage. This leads to cost savings for municipalities and water operators and ensures a more sustainable and reliable water supply for communities.

Mapping and Monitoring of Infiltration/Inflow: Tracking sewer flow over an extended period with sufficient resolution reveals issues such as illicit connections and improper stormwater pipe installations. By addressing these problems, the project contributes to improving the overall health and efficiency of wastewater systems. Detecting and rectifying these issues prevents pollution, mitigates flooding risks, and protects public health, ensuring a safer and cleaner environment for communities. This is particularly useful in areas where there are high amounts of combined surface water systems and sewer systems.

Operational Monitoring and Data Accessibility: Detailed data collection and accessibility through the Environmental Dashboard's and the Nessie System's APIs enable better decision-making in water and wastewater infrastructure projects and for homeowners' personal use. This data facilitates more efficient resource allocation, infrastructure planning, and maintenance scheduling by providing insights into usage patterns, system performance, and higher leakage areas to prioritize. Ultimately, this leads to cost savings, improved service delivery, and better overall management of water resources, benefiting both communities and the environment.

Improving water meter technology, water leakage detection methods, and monitoring sewer I/I is crucial for the water sector to ensure efficient water management and infrastructure maintenance. Advanced water meters provide accurate data on usage and detect leaks early, helping water organizations conserve water and reduce costs. Effective drinking water leakage detection methods, including real-time monitoring, enable prompt identification and repair of leaks, minimizing water losses and infrastructure damage. Mapping and monitoring I/I highlights problems such as illicit connections and improper pipe installations, allowing water organizations to address these issues to maintain the integrity of their wastewater systems. This

comprehensive approach supports sustainable water management, enhances service delivery, and ensures the long-term reliability of water and wastewater infrastructure.

8 Conclusion

In summary, the project's advancements in smart water meter technology, leakage detection algorithms, mapping and monitoring sewer I/I in different environments, and operational monitoring platforms have tested and achieved new water management methods. Enhanced smart water meter technology, with features such as substantial data logging and leak detection capabilities, benefits both homeowners and municipalities by providing accurate water usage information and preventing costly damages from leaking pipes while simultaneously balancing its own power consumption and generation without connection to the electrical grid. The adoption of model-based and data-driven water leakage detection methods improves water management efficiency which in turn conserves water resources, reduces infrastructure damage and minimizes costs associated with locating leakages. Moreover, several leak detection algorithms have been developed and demonstrated in the relevant environment of LL Bodø or representative similar case studies, with a novel artificial benchmark dataset created for future research. Findings that SWMs with high granularity can be used for in-house leakage detection, customer behaviour analysis, demand, and leakage quantification, but are not suited to detect leaks in the distribution system reliably.

Mapping and monitoring infiltration contribute to the overall health and efficiency of wastewater systems by detecting and rectifying issues such as illicit connections, and improper installations and locating old, unregistered combined sewer connection points. Furthermore, detailed data collection and accessibility enable better decision-making in water and wastewater infrastructure projects, leading to cost savings, improved service delivery, and better overall management of water resources. These advancements are crucial for ensuring efficient water management and infrastructure maintenance, ultimately benefiting communities and the environment.

Detailed data collection and accessibility through the Environmental Dashboard's and the Nessie System's APIs enable better decision-making in water and wastewater infrastructure projects and for homeowners' personal use. By providing insights into usage patterns, system performance, and potential areas with higher needs for improvement, this data facilitates more efficient resource allocation, infrastructure planning, and maintenance scheduling. Ultimately, this leads to cost savings, improved service delivery, and better overall management of water resources, benefiting both communities and the environment.

References

- Alaya, S., 2022. Assessment of Pressure-Pipe Life Expectancy and Pressure-Leakage Relationships in the Water Distribution System in Bergen, Norway. A Case Study (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Azwar, E., Nurhajati, 2017. Leak Detection on Water Distribution Networks Using Helium Gas. *Civil and Environmental Research* 9, 20.
- Bach, P.M., Kodikara, J.K., 2017. Reliability of Infrared Thermography in Detecting Leaks in Buried Water Reticulation Pipes. *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Observations Remote Sensing* 10, 4210–4224. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2017.2708817>
- Baldi, P., 2012. Autoencoders, Unsupervised Learning, and Deep Architectures, in: *Proceedings of ICML Workshop on Unsupervised and Transfer Learning*. Presented at the Proceedings of ICML Workshop on Unsupervised and Transfer Learning, JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings, pp. 37–49.
- Beheshti, M., Sægrov, S., 2018. Quantification Assessment of Extraneous Water Infiltration and Inflow by Analysis of the Thermal Behavior of the Sewer Network. *Water* 10, 1070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10081070>
- Beheshti, M., Sægrov, S., Ugarelli, R., 2015. Infiltration/Inflow Assessment and Detection in Urban Sewer System. *Vann* 01, 24–34.
- Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., Clemens-Meyer, F., Lepot, M. (Eds.), 2021. *Metrology in Urban Drainage and Stormwater Management: Plug and Pray*. IWA Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.2166/9781789060119>
- Boyle, T., Giurco, D., Mukheibir, P., Liu, A., Moy, C., White, S., Stewart, R., 2013. Intelligent Metering for Urban Water: A Review. *Water* 5, 1052–1081. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w5031052>
- Colombo, A.F., Lee, P.J., Karney, B.W., 2009. A selective literature review of transient-based leak detection methods. *Journal of Hydro-environment Research* 2, 212–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jher.2009.02.003>
- Cominola, A., Giuliani, M., Piga, D., Castelletti, A., Rizzoli, A.E., 2015. Benefits and challenges of using smart meters for advancing residential water demand modeling and management: A review. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 72, 198–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2015.07.012>
- Daniel, I., Pesantez, J., Letzgus, S., Khaksar Fasaee, M.A., Alghamdi, F., Berglund, E., Mahinthakumar, G., Cominola, A., 2022. A Sequential Pressure-Based Algorithm for Data-Driven Leakage Identification and Model-Based Localization in Water Distribution Networks. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management* 148, 04022025. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WR.1943-5452.0001535](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001535)
- Daulat, S., Roghani, B., Langeveld, J., Rokstad, M.M., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., 2024. Metrics to quantify the degree of co-location of urban water infrastructure. *Water Science and Technology* wst2024191. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2024.191>
- De Bénédictis, J., Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., 2005. Infiltration in sewer systems: comparison of measurement methods. *Water Science and Technology* 52, 219–227. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2005.0079>
- De Coster, A., Pérez Medina, J.L., Nottebaere, M., Alkhalifeh, K., Neyt, X., Vanderdonckt, J., Lambot, S., 2019. Towards an improvement of GPR-based detection of pipes and leaks in water distribution networks. *Journal of Applied Geophysics* 162, 138–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jappgeo.2019.02.001>

- Ellis, J.B., Butler, D., 2015. Surface water sewer misconnections in England and Wales: Pollution sources and impacts. *Science of The Total Environment* 526, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.04.042>
- EPA, 1990. Rainfall Induced Infiltration into Sewer Systems: Report to Congress (No. 430/09-90–005). Environmental Protection Agency, USA.
- Farley, M., 2001. Leakage management and control: A best practice manual. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Habenicht, D., 2023. Benchmarking model-based and model-free leakage detection methods on real-world data (Master). Technical University Berlin, Berlin, Germany.
- Hey, G., Jönsson, K., Mattsson, A., 2016. The impact of infiltration and inflow on wastewater treatment plants: A case study in Sweden (VA-Teknik Södra Rapport No. 6). Lund University.
- Hochreiter, S., Schmidhuber, J., 1997. Long Short-Term Memory. *Neural Computation* 9, 1735–1780. <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>
- Hoes, O.A.C., Schilperoort, R.P.S., Luxemburg, W.M.J., Clemens, F.H.L.R., van de Giesen, N.C., 2009. Locating illicit connections in storm water sewers using fiber-optic distributed temperature sensing. *Water Research* 43, 5187–5197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2009.08.020>
- Hu, Z., Chen, B., Chen, W., Tan, D., Shen, D., 2021. Review of model-based and data-driven approaches for leak detection and location in water distribution systems. *Water Supply* 21, 3282–3306. <https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2021.101>
- Hunaidi, O., Chu, W., Wang, A., Guan, W., 2000. Detecting leaks in plastic pipes. *Journal AWWA* 92, 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1551-8833.2000.tb08819.x>
- Jacobsz, S.W., Jahnke, S.I., 2020. Leak detection on water pipelines in unsaturated ground by discrete fibre optic sensing. *Structural Health Monitoring* 19, 1219–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475921719881979>
- Jaurena Beltrami, M., 2023. On the interconnectivity of urban water system models: Possibilities, limitations, and feasibilities (Master). Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Jenssen Sola, K., Bjerkholt, J.T., Lindholm, O.G., Ratnaweera, H., 2018. Infiltration and Inflow (I/I) to Wastewater Systems in Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland. *Water* 10, 1696. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10111696>
- Jørgensen, T.L., Rostad, M., 2022. bedreVANN – resultater 2022. Tilstandsvurdering av kommunale vann- og avløpstjenester. Norsk Vann BA, Hamar, Norway.
- Kammoun, M., Kammoun, A., Abid, M., 2022. Leak Detection Methods in Water Distribution Networks: A Comparative Survey on Artificial Intelligence Applications. *Journal of Pipeline Systems Engineering and Practice* 13, 04022024. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)PS.1949-1204.0000646](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)PS.1949-1204.0000646)
- Karpf, C., Krebs, P., 2011. Quantification of groundwater infiltration and surface water inflows in urban sewer networks based on a multiple model approach. *Water Research* 45, 3129–3136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2011.03.022>
- Kingma, D.P., Welling, M., 2022. Auto-Encoding Variational Bayes. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1312.6114>
- Klise, K.A., Murray, R., Haxton, T., 2018. An Overview of the Water Network Tool for Resilience (WNTR), in: WDSA / CCWI Joint Conference Proceedings. Presented at the WDSA / CCWI 2018, Kingston, Ontario, Canada.
- Lambert, A., Hirner, W., 2000. Losses from Water Supply Systems: Standard Terminology and Recommended Performance Measures. International Water Association (IWA).
- Lambert, A.O., 2002. International Report: Water losses management and techniques. *Water Supply* 2, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2002.0115>

- Lepot, M., Makris, K.F., Clemens, F.H.L.R., 2017. Detection and quantification of lateral, illicit connections and infiltration in sewers with Infra-Red camera: Conclusions after a wide experimental plan. *Water Research* 122, 678–691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.06.030>
- Leutnant, D., Döring, A., Uhl, M., 2019. swmmr - an R package to interface SWMM. *Urban Water Journal* 16, 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2019.1611889>
- Li, J., Yang, X., Sitzenfrei, R., 2020. Rethinking the Framework of Smart Water System: A Review. *Water* 12, 412. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12020412>
- Liu, Z., Kleiner, Y., 2013. State of the art review of inspection technologies for condition assessment of water pipes. *Measurement* 46, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2012.05.032>
- Løfald, A., 2023. Using Optical Velocimetry to Detect Illicit Inflow to Sewers: A Sensor Strategy (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Lund, N.S.V., Kirstein, J.K., Madsen, H., Mark, O., Mikkelsen, P.S., Borup, M., 2021. Feasibility of using smart meter water consumption data and in-sewer flow observations for sewer system analysis: a case study. *Journal of Hydroinformatics* 23, 795–812. <https://doi.org/10.2166/hydro.2021.166>
- Lundblad, U., Backö, J., 2012. Undersökningsmetoder för att hitta källorna till tillskottsvatten (No. 2012–13). *Svenskt Vatten Utveckling (SVU)*, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Meier, R., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., Steffelbauer, D.B., Makropoulos, C., 2022. Flow Measurements Derived from Camera Footage Using an Open-Source Ecosystem. *Water* 14, 424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14030424>
- Mohan Doss, P., Totland, M., Rokstad, M.M., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., 2023. A comparative study of Encoder-Decoder Models for Leak Detection in Water Distribution Networks, in: *Proceedings of 19th International Computing and Control for Water Industry Conference*. Leicester, UK.
- Mohan Doss, P., Totland, M., Steffelbauer, D., Piller, O., Rokstad, M.M., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., 2022. A hybrid leak detection framework using variational autoencoder surrogates, in: *Proceedings of Water Loss 2022*. IWA (Int. Water Assoc.), Prague, Czech Republic.
- Moy de Vitry, M., Schneider, M.Y., Wani, O., Manny, L., Leitão, J.P., Eggimann, S., 2019. Smart urban water systems: what could possibly go wrong? *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14, 081001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab3761>
- Mutikanga, H.E., Sharma, S.K., Vairavamoorthy, K., 2013. Methods and Tools for Managing Losses in Water Distribution Systems. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management* 139, 166–174. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WR.1943-5452.0000245](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0000245)
- Nordahl, E., 2022. Leak Localization with the Dual Model on a Real-World Water Distribution System (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Norsk Vann Rapport 239, 2018. Beregning av bærekraftig lekkasjenivå. Norsk Vann BA, Hamar, Norway.
- Norsk Vann Rapport 255, 2020. Bærekraftig fremmedvannandel – modell for vurdering av riktig nivå. Norsk Vann BA, Hamar, Norway.
- Norsk Vann Rapport 259, 2021. Kommunalt investeringsbehov for vann og avløp 2021 – 2040. Norsk Vann BA, Hamar, Norway.
- Ohlin Saletti, A., 2021. Infiltration and inflow to wastewater sewer systems - A literature review on risk management and decision support. Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Ohlin Saletti, A., Lindhe, A., Söderqvist, T., Rosén, L., 2023. Cost to society from infiltration and inflow to wastewater systems. *Water Research* 229, 119505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119505>

- OIML R 49-1, 2013. Water meters for cold potable water and hot water. Part 1: Metrological and technical requirements (International Recommendation). International Organization of Legal Metrology.
- Panasiuk, O., Hedström, A., Langeveld, J., Viklander, M., 2022. Identifying sources of infiltration and inflow in sanitary sewers in a northern community: comparative assessment of selected methods. *Water Science and Technology* 86, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2022.151>
- Pangle, L.A., Diem, J.E., Milligan, R., Adams, E., Murray, A., 2022. Contextualizing Inflow and Infiltration Within the Streamflow Regime of Urban Watersheds. *Water Resources Research* 58, e2021WR030406. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR030406>
- Paszke, A., Gross, S., Massa, F., Lerer, A., Bradbury, J., Chanan, G., Killeen, T., Lin, Z., Gimelshein, N., Antiga, L., Desmaison, A., Köpf, A., Yang, E., DeVito, Z., Raison, M., Tejani, A., Chilamkurthy, S., Steiner, B., Fang, L., Bai, J., Chintala, S., 2019. PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1912.01703>
- Pietrosanto, A., Carratù, M., Liguori, C., 2021. Sensitivity of water meters to small leakage. *Measurement* 168, 108479. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2020.108479>
- Puust, R., Kapelan, Z., Savic, D.A., Koppel, T., 2010. A review of methods for leakage management in pipe networks. *Urban Water Journal* 7, 25–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15730621003610878>
- Santos Clotas, E., Sarrias Monton, M., Casals del Busto, I., Kossieris, P., Pantazis, C., Spartalis, I., Kristiansen, V., Lyngstad, S., Collette, R., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., Muthanna, T.M., Bosco, C., Ugarelli, R., Vennesland, A., Manouri, S., Kroll, S., Raes, B., Joris, I., Van Bauwel, F., Ribeiro, R., Rosa, M.J., Coelho, S.T., Mendes, R., Remedios, S., Fernandes, J., Cardoso, P., Storelli, D., Vedruccio, A., Ragazzo, P., Chiuccchini, N., Franceschetti, P., Gatto, O., Lykou, A., Makropoulos, C., 2023. The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release (Deliverable No. 3.4), B-Watersmart.
- Schafer, R., 2011. What Is a Savitzky-Golay Filter? *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* 28, 111–117. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2011.941097>
- Shavi, S., Tscheikner-Gratl, F., Muthanna, T.M., 2021. Technological indicators for water-smartness (Deliverable No. 2.1), B-Watersmart.
- Silva, C., Cardoso, M.A., Rosa, M.J., Alegre, H., Ugarelli, R., Bosco, C., Raspati, G., Azrague, K., Bruaset, S., Damman, S., Koop, S., Munaretto, S., Conceição, M.M.S. da, Gomes, C., Rosell, L.F., Schmuck, A., Strehl, C., Doss, P.M., 2023. Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework (Deliverable No. 6.3), B-Watersmart.
- Skagsoset, C., 2023. Quantifying Infiltration and Inflow in Data-Scarce Environments: Possibilities and Co-benefits for Municipalities (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Sola, A.K.J., Kvaal, K., Bjerkholt, J.T., Lindholm, O.G., Ratnaweera, H., 2019. Identifying factors influencing Infiltration and Inflow-water (I/I-water) in wastewater systems -using multivariate data analysis. *Vann* 4, 263–277.
- Sola, K.J., Bjerkholt, J.T., Lindholm, O.G., Ratnaweera, H., 2020. Analysing consequences of infiltration and inflow water (I/I-water) using cost-benefit analyses. *Water Science and Technology* 82, 1312–1326. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2020.395>
- Søvik, S., 2021. Long Short-Term Memory for Detection of Inflow and Infiltration Water in Sewer Systems: A Case Study from Bergen Municipality (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Srivastava, N., Mansimov, E., Salakhutdinov, R., 2016. Unsupervised Learning of Video Representations using LSTMs. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1502.04681>

- Steffelbauer, D., 2018. Model-Based Leak Localization in Water Distribution Systems (PhD). Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria.
- Steffelbauer, D.B., Deuerlein, J., Gilbert, D., Abraham, E., Piller, O., 2022. Pressure-Leak Duality for Leak Detection and Localization in Water Distribution Systems. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management* 148, 04021106. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WR.1943-5452.0001515](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001515)
- Tornyeviadzi, H.M., Seidu, R., 2023. Leakage detection in water distribution networks via 1D CNN deep autoencoder for multivariate SCADA data. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 122, 106062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106062>
- Totland, M., 2022. Detection of leakages in a water distribution network using an autoencoder (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Truong, C., Oudre, L., Vayatis, N., 2020. Selective review of offline change point detection methods. *Signal Processing* 167, 107299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2019.107299>
- Ugarelli, R., Damman, S., Koop, S., Alegre, H., Cardoso, M.A., Almeida, M. do C., Oliveira, R., Vildåsen, S.S., Raspati, G., Barrero, M.J.A., Termes, M., Mateo, M.R., Schmuck, A., Strehl, C., Lekawska-Andrinopoulou, L., 2021. What is water-smartness and how to assess it? (Deliverable No. 6.1), BWatersmart.
- Van Assel, J., Kroll, S., Delgado, R., 2023. Calculation of Dry Weather Flows in Pumping Stations to Identify Inflow and Infiltration in Urban Drainage Systems. *Water* 15, 864. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15050864>
- Vimme, J., 2021. Water Loss Management and Data Quality Assessment in Medium-Sized Water Distribution Systems in Norway: A Case Study of Arendal Municipality in Norway (Master). Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Vrachimis, S.G., Eliades, D.G., Taormina, R., Kapelan, Z., Ostfeld, A., Liu, S., Kyriakou, M., Pavlou, P., Qiu, M., Polycarpou, M.M., 2022. Battle of the Leakage Detection and Isolation Methods. *J. Water Resour. Plann. Manage.* 148, 04022068. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WR.1943-5452.0001601](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001601)
- Wang, X.J., Simpson, A.R., Lambert, M., Vítkovský, J., 2001. Leak detection in pipeline systems using hydraulic methods: a review, in: *Conference on Hydraulics in Civil Engineering*. Hobart, Australia, pp. 391–400.
- Weiß, G., Brombach, H., Haller, B., 2002. Infiltration and inflow in combined sewer systems: long-term analysis. *Water Science and Technology* 45, 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2002.0112>
- Ye, L., Qian, Y., Zhu, D.Z., Huang, B., 2023. Inflow and infiltration assessment of a prototype sanitary sewer network in a coastal city in China. *Water Science and Technology* 88, 2940–2954. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2023.386>
- Zhang, Q., Zheng, F., Jia, Y., Savic, D., Kapelan, Z., 2021. Real-time foul sewer hydraulic modelling driven by water consumption data from water distribution systems. *Water Research* 188, 116544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116544>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.